

An Edge System for the Safety of Cyclists in the Urban Area

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Abstract—Urban areas are evolving towards systems based on sustainable mobility. In particular, thanks to technologies such as Big Data analysis, Cloud, Edge Computing, and IoT, it is possible to design both decision support services for the management of smart cities and services for users. The proposed work presents an innovative device for the safety of cyclists in urban areas. The device is designed to ensure continuous connectivity. Connectivity can be global (via internet) or local thanks to the use of the mesh network. Furthermore, the designed infrastructure provides cyclists with real-time information on the urban area they are crossing, starting from the data collected by the smart city. During the implementation phase, it was of particular interest to test the functioning of the mesh and the energy performance of the device in the field.

Index Terms—Mesh Network; Edge Computing; Internet of Things; Mobility; Urban Mobility;

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's cities are facing a revolutionary era in urban mobility due to several factors, such as their continuous growth and the concentration of human activities. To prevent and solve mobility-related problems, such as traffic congestion, air pollution, and their potential link with health risks, cities are investigating new solutions for improving urban mobility to meet the actual demand of citizens living or moving around the cities every day. The European Union encourages projects in the field of Smart Mobility and Sustainable Mobility [1]. One of these is the URBANITE project [2], funded under the EU-H2020 funding program.

One of the main objectives of URBANITE is to promote the use of disruptive technologies in emerging Smart Cities, for example through the use and analysis of Big Data, AI (Artificial Intelligence) algorithms, etc. The aim of the project is to provide end users with a series of smart technological tools able to support innovative digital transformation in urban mobility management. The main challenge of the city of Messina for the next few years is twofold: on the one hand, it wants to build new mobility services able to satisfy the needs of citizens, and visitors, allowing them to move

and cross the city with continuous services; on the other hand, the challenge consists in optimizing the management and interaction between the different mobility and monitoring systems, and services available in the urban area of the city of Messina, reducing waste of resources and costs for the Public Administration. Starting from the Messina use case, this work proposes the design and prototype of a device that can be usefully adopted to provide value-added urban mobility services within the city.

With this work, we want to propose a device that increases the safety of bicycle users in urban areas. The prototyped device must be connected to an electric bike and continuously powered. The Edge Device is able to collect data on the user's cycling performance and share it with other cyclists through a designed mesh network. In this way, cyclists provide information that enriches the dataset of data collected by the sensors in the smart city, which are subsequently processed within the central city cloud.

The increase in safety for the cyclist depends on the ability of the device to provide the user with information about the surrounding environment, to allow him to have a complete overview of what is happening in terms of mobility. The problem addressed focuses on the ability of a device to acquire information from the device, process it, and provide it to the user. Furthermore, the ability of the device to operate for an adequate time without the need for main power is evaluated to assess whether the system is usable during urban travel.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: section II describes the state of the art regarding the area analyzed. Section III report the motivation at the base of the paper. In the section IV, V and VI the design of the work, the enabling technologies and the implementation are respectively described. The tests carried out are reported in the section VII, the conclusions and future scenarios analyzed are discussed in the section VIII.

II. RELATED WORKS

Nowadays, smart cities are moving towards new perspectives of sustainable mobility adopting smart models that see the bicycle as the most used transportation by citizens. Electric and

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non-electric bicycles are used both for normal daily commuting and sporting activities. Furthermore, moving around with a bicycle daily can lead to positive results on health. In [3] a system is proposed that uses smartphone sensors and additional devices to collect information on users' cycling routines. In particular, through the accelerometer of the mobile phone, it is possible to detect the falls of cyclists also providing necessary support in case of accidents. In [4] the authors present a smart bike with a monitoring system for cyclists via the IoT (Internet of Things). The system allows real-time monitoring of the cyclist in terms of health and performance conditions. Monitoring is done using heart rate, pulse oximetry, magnetic reed sensors, and GPS (Global Positioning System) modules. The sensors are connected to the microcontroller, to the Wi-Fi module, and, the data is accessible via an IoT platform or application. The work presented included the mounting of sensors on the bike while others monitor the cyclist. The application interface displays parameters such as heart rate, pulse oximetry, speed, distance traveled, and position for the cyclist and trainer to monitor their health and that of the cyclist during training or tournament. The Connected Bike project is presented in [5]. Even in this work, the authors use a variety of technologies, both hardware, and software, to provide cycling enthusiasts with a modern alternative training solution. A trainer can monitor online, through a web application, some of the important parameters for training, in particular the speed, cadence, and power generated by the cyclist. In addition, the trainer can see the cyclist's position with the help of a GPS module. To acquire data with a low percentage of error, the devices inserted on the bicycles must be equipped with calibrated sensors. Sensor calibration is a very delicate subject and subject to numerous studies. In particular, in [6], [7] the effects of aging on the sensors are analyzed and an on-the-edge self-calibration system is implemented.

Furthermore, in the literature, there are different IoT-based solutions for sports analysis, which aim to improve performance, coaching, and strategic information. The authors in [8] present a report on the experience of using cutting-edge IoT technologies in cycling. In this study a group of cyclists can form a reliable and energy-efficient mesh network to collect and process real-time sensor data, such as heart rate, speed, and location. The collected data is analyzed in real-time to estimate the performance of each cyclist and obtain immediate feedback. The information drawn from the tracking of journeys with cycles can also provide information on how the vehicle is used [9]. In general, commercial vendors provide large volumes of data unspecified, but their products are used primarily for motorized travel or are in the early stages of development. Readily available data sources and their applications are more focused on modality-specified data, which has enabled several non-motorized travel studies, including travel pattern identification, route choice modeling, exposure to accidents, air pollution, and evaluating the provision of new facilities - but mainly focus on cycling. In their study, the authors focus on issues related to privacy and the accuracy of the data collected. In this case, it is important the access control and the security of the data [10].

In [11] the results obtained from a Sustainable Mobility

project in Messina are described. The application presented aims to encourage citizens to use low-impact vehicles instead of private cars. Through a partnership between different stakeholders, a digital application was developed to assign electric bicycles to citizens, free of charge for a limited period. The authors describe the IT security problems, both in terms of secure authentication for citizens who access the service, and in terms of traceability of the entire assignment process. The flow is described from the user's request to the return of the e-bike. The solution adopted uses two-factor authentication (2FA) and Blockchain as the main technologies being implemented.

Innovative and advanced smart devices and virtual devices are described in [12]. Authors have designed, for one use case in the city of Messina, an abstracted component characterized by specific high-level functionalities. The system offers the chance to access the needed information with the most appropriate frequency and accuracy, avoiding information overload and allowing a more efficient computation. In [13] authors show the use of customized generic Edge devices to carry out multiple activities at the same time, also focusing on how the proposed solution can lighten the work of cloud infrastructures. The presented concepts were implemented and tested in a real use case in the city of Messina by means Function as a Service (FaaS) paradigm. The proposed work allows users to perform multiple tasks on the same device. From the studies carried out, it emerges that monitoring the performance of cyclists is a very important issue. Several studies have been carried out for data acquisition, monitoring led to increte results. From the state of the art, it emerged that data on mobility are collected in various different cities, and, also in Messina (use case of the URBANITE project). The proposed work aims to combine the data collected by a specific device and the data available on the data lake in the city to create an always-connected information system for bicycle users in urban areas. The designed device allows cyclists in the same geographical area to have always updated information that takes into account the situation in real-time in the city. Finally, the proposed work aims to demonstrate that the simultaneous use of low-cost sensors allows realizing an innovative device that allows to carry out the required switching.

III. MOTIVATION

Public administrations, as well as companies, are trying to study the traffic flows that move in the smart city. The interest in this issue is given by the fact that more and more people move by different means, and therefore it is necessary to guarantee the control of greenhouse gas emissions but at the same time efficient services. Bicycles are becoming increasingly important in urban mobility. These are vehicles that can move even with zero emissions without causing large traffic flows. In many cities, however, the culture of using the bicycle has not yet been consolidated, this is one of the factors that cause danger for those who use it. Moreover, to encourage the population to use the bike it is necessary to guarantee the safety of this transportation through a new concept of

community that makes the vehicle always connected and reachable.

Fig. 1. Reference Scenario.

The idea behind this paper is to design and prototype a software system consisting of Edge devices and a cloud system. Edge devices must collect data to be sent to the cloud and ensure a continuous connection with other devices of the same "family" geographically close to each other (Fig. 1). However, the device is based on a cloud that collects and processes data to be provided to users of the system or to support the AI algorithms. Furthermore, the system proposed aims to create a sort of social network between users of green vehicles in urban areas. Thanks to the prototype presented in this work, it will be possible to share routes, alarm events in the case of illness or accident, and share dangers on the road or points of interest in real-time. Our challenge is to design a system that is hybrid concerning connection technologies and therefore is always connected with nearby devices via a mesh network, while connected to the world via a 4g/5g connection and sends data to the cloud. Furthermore, the impact that this type of technology has on energy consumption will be investigated in order to verify its feasibility.

IV. DESIGN

The high-level reference architecture of the proposed solution is shown in Fig. 2.

The System Architecture is composed of 4 main levels and different components that communicate with each other through REST API:

- Sensing Layer: is the data acquisition layer, and it is composed of 2 components:
 - Data Collector: this component acquires sensor data. It is optimized for the specific sensor that sends data;
 - Abstraction layer: prepares the data for the top layer. This component represents the interface with the Data Layer;
- Data Layer: it defines the storage and pre-analysis capabilities of the data before it is used. This layer consists of:
 - Storage DFS: it is a distributed file system that maintains the data collected by the Sensing Layer. This component mainly deals with providing data to the Cloud Communication component which is an agent that transfers data to the Cloud through

Fig. 2. General Architecture.

the Connection Layer in presence of an available connection;

- Pseudo - Real-Time Event Management: this component is composed of an agent that based on the acquired data can trigger an event (i.e. turn on a led, send an alarm) or perform a pre-processing on the data. Data processing is required to interact with the front-end, and the system user via the User-Agent Communication or with the mesh network via the Mesh Agent Communication. The Mesh Agent Communication through the Communication Layer allows communication between the single Edge Device and the Mesh Network.
- Management Layer: is the architectural core component. This layer aims to guarantee high-quality service in terms of accuracy of the information provided and must ensure efficient management of the energy used by the Edge device. Management Layer coordinates all data acquisitions and their processing as well as monitoring communications and all energy consumption concerning every single operation. In this layer algorithms contribute to the optimization of processes;
- Communication Layer: It defines the communication protocols between the device and the outside. Depending on the recipient of the message, it uses BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy) or WIFI (Wireless Fidelity) protocol or even both for connection with a mesh network. The connection with the cloud is managed by 4G/5G technology.

In the use case of Messina, the Cloud component in the above architecture has been enriched with new dedicated components at the Edge level, which fully integrate the existing Cloud ecosystem, as shown in Fig. 3. In particular, a local component called *Messina Data Storage* has been added. This component acts as a support for the parent component

Fig. 3. Messina-URBANITE Architecture.

Data Storage & Retrieval (reported in URBANITE Cloud Components) through the *Data Harvester & Preparation* and is filled with data by the *Data Importer*. The *Data Processor* allows both to expose the data via Restful API and to process them ensuring correct formatting. Finally, within the *Urbanite UI*, three new specific components for the Messina use case have been built: *Messina Traffic Evolution*, *Messina Traffic Flows*, *Messina LPT Critical Areas*. As well as available for URBANITE UI, the REST APIs are made available to interface with the Level 2 proposed in the general architecture.

Fig. 4 describes the high-level architecture of the Edge device.

Fig. 4. Edge Device Architecture.

The Edge device is composed of several components that interact with each other:

- **Computing Unit:** it constitutes the core of the device. It contains the computing unit and all the components necessary for interacting with the external components;

- **Battery:** it is an external rechargeable device that powers the system;
- **Memory:** it allows data to be stored permanently;
- **Communication unit:** it is a unit used for communication between the computing unit and the sensors external to the device. The communication can be BLE, WI-FI, etc;
- **Internal sensor:** they are sensors that allow the detection of data and are located inside the device. Examples are the accelerometer for detecting acceleration, and the GPS receiver for locating the bike. The system can also integrate sensors for medical use to evaluate the cyclist's physical performance;
- **External Sensor:** these are sensors that can be placed on the bicycle or on the cyclist to allow the acquisition of specific data. One example is a reed sensor needed to evaluate the pedaling cadence and the wheel rotation frequency;
- **Touch screen:** it allows the user to interact with the Edge Device.

V. OVERVIEW REFERENCE TECHNOLOGIES

In this section, we will describe the hardware and software technologies used for the realization of a prototype of the Edge device. The presented device allows users to have information on the instant speed of the bike, travel distance, slope of the road, inclination of the bicycle, and ambient temperature. In addition, sensors will be used to calculate the pedaling cadence

A. Hardware technologies

- **Raspberry Pi W Zero:** it is a single board created in 2017 by the Raspberry Pi Foundation and represents the Computing Unit of the Edge device. Energy consumption is the particular strength of this model. It is estimated that in cases of maximum use of resources, consumption is around 1W. This feature makes it easy to use the device even with a battery. Furthermore, the small dimensions (65mm × 30mm × 5mm) make it suitable for the required use. As for connectivity, the card is equipped with an 802.11n 2.4 GHz wireless LAN connection and a Bluetooth 4.1 Low Energy connection. The slot for the micro SD comes used for both loading the operating system and storing data. The Raspberry Pi W Zero is equipped with a Broadcom BCM2835 system-on-chip, with an ARM11 microprocessor running at 1GHz and has 512 MB of ram. It is possible to connect other components to the board through the GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) connector.
- **GPS Neo 6M:** it is a GPS (Global Positioning System) receiver with a ceramic antenna and a backup battery that can keep data. It has a 5Hz position update rate 50 channel receiver. The module interfaces with the raspberry via the I2C (Inter-Integrated Circuit) protocol, and it can be powered from 3 to 5 Volt. Using this GPS receiver it is possible to obtain the geographic coordinates of the place where the bicycle is located, in addition, other data such as altitude and time of detection are also available.

- **MPU-6050:** MPU-6050 sensor contains a 3-axis MEMS (Micro Electronic Mechanical Systems) accelerometer and a 3-axis MEMS gyroscope in a single integrated circuit. Thanks to the accelerometer it is possible to measure the acceleration in one direction. It uses a 16-bit analog to digital converter and can capture channels x, y, and z at the same time. The sensor interfaces with the raspberry via the I2C communication protocol. It can be powered with a voltage from 3V to 5V. Thanks to the three acceleration measurement axes, it is possible to calculate, with the appropriate physical and mathematical formulas, the degree of road slope as well as being able to calculate the lateral inclination of the bicycle. Furthermore, the sensor can detect ambient temperature.
- **Reed LM393:** LM393 and is equipped with a Reed contact (single contact normally open), a trimmer for adjusting the sensitivity, a status LED for the power supply, and an output signal LED. It allows obtaining a digital output signal depending on whether the Reed contact is open or closed. Just approach at a distance of at least 2 cm, a magnet to close the contact. The module interfaces with the raspberry via the I2C communication protocol and can be powered with a voltage from 3 to 5 V. Using two reed sensors, one mounted on the front wheel of the bicycle and one mounted on one of the pedals, it is possible to calculate various parameters useful for monitoring cycling activity: speed snapshot, distance traveled, and pedaling cadence.

B. Software Technology

- **Mesh Network:** it is a communication network composed of radio nodes organized in a mesh topology. In particular, it can be defined as an interconnection between MCU or MPU-based devices (nodes). If the nodes move constantly or frequently, the mesh increases its computational load. When a node stops working within the mesh, the other nodes continue to communicate, either directly or through other intermediate nodes. Wireless mesh networks can self-form and self-configure. A mesh network can be both WI-FI and Bluetooth. In the case in question, this network topology lends itself to the presence of temporary nodes in an area of the city;
- **BATMAN (Better Approach To Mobile Ad-hoc Networking):** is a routing protocol for multi-hop ad-hoc mesh mobile networks. On the BATMAN-based mesh network, Originator Messages are sent at regular intervals, until they are received by the recipient at least once or until the packet is lost. Each packet loss allows you to go to find the best path from the node to node. Furthermore, the number of originator messages received by a given node is used to make a qualitative estimate of the route. The number of originator messages received is stored in a table (originator list) with which it is possible to calculate the best next-hop for the whole network. This feature makes the protocol optimized for use by cyclists circulating in urban areas.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the prototype focused on the construction of the device and its configuration. Each sensor is configured in order to acquire a different type of data. After the acquisition, the data are processed, shown on the device, sent to the mesh network, and eventually to the cloud. Once started, the device connects to the mesh network or a WiFi network by configuring itself. After the start-up phase, the user will see a screen like the one shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Main screen device.

From the main screen, the user can have various information and also enter personal data that the device will request to offer a better service. As the user proceeds with the march, the device shows information (Fig. 6). Some of this information comes from direct acquisitions, while others come from the mesh network and/or the cloud. The mesh network is still

Fig. 6. Screen device with data.

capable of working without connecting to the cloud. The possibility of the nodes having processing capacity on the Edge allows obtaining information about the users who are using the device. This ability makes it possible to provide services that increase the personal safety of users by encouraging them to use the bicycle. The problem concerning this application, however, concerns precisely the intended use of network

resources. To evaluate the impact of the use of resources for this type of application, benchmarks have been prepared for the evaluation of energy consumption. The assessments made will be discussed in the next section.

VII. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiments were carried out with the aim of demonstrating the possibility of using the Edge device in a real environment. Energy consumption and data exchange capacity were identified as critical aspects in the use of the device. Edge Device is a Raspberry Pi W zero powered by a battery with a nominal voltage of 3.7 V and a full load capacity of 3000 mAh.

A. Computational core consumption

The first test concerned the estimation of Raspberry consumption in different conditions of use and related connectivity activation.

Fig. 7. Raspberry consumption.

As shown in Fig. 7 from test data carried out, it emerged that in idle mode the raspberry absorbs a current of 40 mAh, while with high CPU usage the device has an absorption of 150mAh. If, in addition, the WIFI functionality is activated, the consumption is 170 mAh, while if the Bluetooth function is activated, the consumption is 160 mAh. If both functions are activated, the total consumption is 210 mAh. It was interesting to evaluate the consumption of the different sensors used in the prototype made. The results of the tests are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Sensors consumption.

The tests showed that the GPS receiver has a consumption of 20 mAh, the accelerometer of 15 mAh, while the sensor reed

has a consumption of 15 mAh (considering that two are used, the total consumption is 30 mAh). The LCD touch screen has a power consumption of 145 mA. Based on the test results, in the worst-case scenario, in which the device works at full load with Bluetooth and WIFI connectivity and all sensors connected, the total current consumption will be:

$$210mAh + 20mAh + 15mAh + 30mAh + 145mAh = 420mAh$$

The battery has a full load capacity of 3000 mAh, this means that the device in the worst case can be used for a time of 7.15 hours. This usage time ensures its functionality for the use case under consideration.

B. Mesh network coverage

A tool called iPerf was used to evaluate the coverage of the WIFI mesh network, in particular its bandwidth and performance. The tests were carried out by varying the distance between the targets and evaluating the quality and the transmission rate of the signal even in the presence of obstacles. The tests in the absence of obstacles are carried out with devices placed each time at a distance of 1, 10, and 20 meters from each other.

Fig. 9. Signal quality without obstacles.

Fig. 10. Transmission rate without obstacles.

As shown in Fig. 9 and 10, if the devices are placed at a distance of 1 meter, the measured signal quality is equal to 95%, while the average data transfer speed is equal to 52 Mbit/s. If the devices are placed at a distance of 10 meters from each other, the signal quality is 65% and the average data transfer rate is 38 Mbit/s. With devices placed at a distance of

20 meters from each other, the signal quality decreases to 58% and the average data transfer rate drops to 31 Mbit/s. Another test phase involved the evaluation of the signal quality and the transmission rate in the presence of obstacles. The results are shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12.

Fig. 11. Signal quality with obstacles.

Fig. 12. Transmission rate with obstacles.

With the devices placed at a distance of 2 meters from each other, and the presence of an obstacle of 25 cm, a signal quality of 80% and an average transfer speed of 47 Mbit/s were measured. In the case of devices placed at a distance of 6 meters, with the presence of 2 obstacles each 25 cm thick placed at a distance of 1 meter, a signal quality of 66% and an average transfer speed of 34 Mbit/s was measured. While, when the devices are placed at a distance of 8 meters, with the presence of 2 obstacles with a thickness of 25 cm at a distance of 1 meter, a signal quality of 56% and an average transfer speed of 29 Mbit/s were measured. The results obtained allow us to conclude that the mesh network has good performance in open spaces without obstacles, which makes it ideal for being used as a network to interconnect the various bikes with each other.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This document presents new technologies to increase the safety of bicycle users in urban areas. The key idea is to assemble a device with an electric bike to ensure continuous connection and collection of cycling performance data. The device is designed to create a mesh network with devices in use by other cyclists, thus creating ad hoc communications and interactions. We implemented a prototype of the proposed

solution and performed some experiments, thus demonstrating its operation. Future works include testing the system by introducing data models based on the NGSI-LD protocol. The aim is to understand if and how complex data management can affect the performance of the device. Furthermore, it is interesting to replace the Edge device used in this paper with cheaper devices and compare the test results to identify a better solution in terms of system feasibility.

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